

Sleep Quality and Sound: Insights from Hospitalized Patients

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ABSTRACT

Advancements in technology and the resulting dehumanization of medical environments, combined with a focus on organizational efficiency, have created significant challenges for the quality of care and the well-being of healthcare professionals. Sleep quality is critical in hospitalised patients' physical and mental recovery, with the hospital soundscape being a major factor affecting rest. This contribution adopts a holistic perspective on the well-being of both patients and caregivers, utilizing user-centred design and open innovation methodologies to establish a shared understanding of the relationship between sleep quality and sound. To get this, the study integrates knowledge from hospitalized patients by collecting valuable insights into how sound impacts sleep quality. The gathered data is analyzed to uncover opportunities for improvement and define design specifications. The initiative aims to identify needs and solutions related to sound while fostering a user-centred approach with a unified language across stakeholders. The findings of this study will serve as the first step of a roadmap, providing design specifications and guidelines for improving sleep quality through sound. These contributions will not only guide future research and development but also redefine the medical care concept, ultimately enhancing patient well-being.

1. INTRODUCTION

The significance of rest for patient recovery is an increasingly explored topic in medicine and healthcare. Proper rest, particularly quality sleep, is essential for physiological recovery, enabling the body to repair tissues, consolidate memory, and regenerate the immune system. Numerous studies have shown that sleep deprivation can negatively impact the immune system, increasing susceptibility to infections and complicating recovery from acute and chronic illnesses (NIH, 2021; Helvig et al., 2016).

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Moreover, rest plays a critical role in the mental and emotional recovery of patients. Insufficient or poor-quality sleep can exacerbate stress and anxiety symptoms, affecting mental health and pain perception—factors that interfere with recovery. For instance, studies have documented that patients who receive adequate rest report lower pain levels and improved overall well-being, optimizing their recovery and quality of life (Cambridge University Press, 2020).

Rest also contributes to stabilizing vital functions such as glucose regulation and blood pressure, which are key factors for patients with chronic conditions like diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. In general, prioritizing rest, including both sleep and wakeful relaxation, allows for better organization of physiological resources to combat illness and promote healing (American River Healthcare, 2022).

The impact of sound on rest quality is a widely studied topic, particularly in hospital and urban environments. Exposure to environmental noise, such as traffic, or socio-technological noise, such as medical alarms or healthcare staff activity in intensive care units (ICUs), disrupts the deep sleep phases necessary for patients' physical and mental recovery. Studies indicate that these noises can prolong the time needed to fall asleep and reduce the amount of slow-wave sleep, which is crucial for physiological recovery and immune function (NIH, 2021; Sleep Foundation, 2021).

Some interventions have shown positive effects in mitigating the impact of noise on sleep. For example, exposure to white noise (continuous low-frequency sounds) appears to help reduce the time required to fall asleep, although the benefits vary depending on the characteristics of the noise and the environment. In hospital settings, the use of headphones or earplugs has been shown to improve rest quality by decreasing the number of nighttime awakenings and enhancing patients' subjective perception of sleep (Sleep Foundation, 2021; Basner et al., 2011).

Music has also proven to be an effective intervention for improving sleep quality. Studies have shown that listening to music before bedtime reduces anxiety and promotes deeper rest, even in patients with mild sleep

disorders. However, this intervention is more effective in cases of mild or subclinical insomnia, with benefits increasing over prolonged exposure (Frontiers, 2019). These findings emphasize the importance of managing soundscapes in healthcare settings to optimize patient rest and, consequently, their recovery.

The phenomenon of complex soundscapes, such as those in hospitals, has been extensively studied. In such settings, sounds play a crucial role in directing actions and facilitating staff coordination, where alarms, surgical tools, and conversations contribute to an "acoustic biotope" guiding attention and immediate responses (Özcan et al., 2022). Ecological approaches to operating room acoustics suggest that studying and improving these environments can lead to effective acoustic interventions that enhance surgical team precision, staff well-being, and patient rest (Johannesma & Aertsen, 1979; Aletta et al., 2020).

This project serves as a preliminary phase for replicating research conducted in the Netherlands on the impact of sound sources on hospitalized patients' rest in a neurology ward. Lenzi et al. (2023) in *Disturbed Sleep: Estimating Night-Time Sound Annoyance at a Hospital Ward* analyzed nocturnal sound events and their perceived annoyance levels among patients. The aim was to develop a model informing healthcare staff about the impact of specific sounds on patient sleep quality, providing a design tool to mitigate the negative effects of hospital acoustic environments. The study involved identifying and classifying sound events, analyzing over 9,000 nocturnal sound events across 429 recordings, categorized into nine types (e.g., snoring, speech, alarms, mechanical sounds). Patients' perceived annoyance was measured using a scale of 1 to 3 for each event. Proposed solutions included staff training in noise reduction, redesigning equipment and spaces, and integrating the data into an algorithm for real-time detection of disruptive sound events. This would enable staff to manage noise sources more effectively, improving the nighttime patient experience.

This new research serves as a precursor to replicating the *Disturbed Sleep* study, aiming to investigate how sound sources affect hospitalized patients in specific wards. The objective is to develop a qualitative study of the environment and its users, guiding the next phase of quantitative research involving sleep monitoring in patients. Key actions include defining sleep quality parameters and descriptors concerning sound. This contribution focuses exclusively on the research conducted with patients, analyzing how sound sources impact their rest and recovery in hospital settings. In subsequent phases, the study will be expanded to include investigating other key stakeholders, such as clinical staff and experts from fields like sound-driven design, machine learning, and user-centered interface design. These future stages will aim to integrate diverse perspectives, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the acoustic environment and its effects, and enabling the

co-creation of solutions that address the needs of all involved parties. Additionally, creating a shared vocabulary among all stakeholders will guide specifications for the next phase and provide a roadmap for implementing actions that will contribute to evolving medical care concepts and enhancing patient well-being.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study 1 - Environment

The first study in the research focused on an objective analysis of the hospital environment during a night shift, from the patient's perspective. The procedure involved collecting and examining all sound events occurring during a single night in a patient's room.

A female patient hospitalized in the neurology ward, in a private room, participated in this phase. The research team was allowed to accompany her throughout the night. The patient was selected based on the following criteria recommended by the ward supervisor: sufficient space in the room to accommodate the researcher, the patient's and her family's consent and willingness to participate, and her location in the neurology ward.

Ideally, this environmental investigation would have been conducted in a double room, as it would have provided a richer sound environment. However, the patients who approved our presence were either in individual rooms or did not have roommates.

The procedure was as follows: the researcher entered the patient's room after dinner and visiting hours, at 9:00 PM, and remained there until the nurses' first morning round at 6:00 AM the next day. During this period, the room was occupied by the hospitalized patient in bed, a caregiver in a chair, and the researcher in another chair.

Sound events were documented using pen and paper, noting their type, frequency, and duration (categorized as momentary, prolonged, or constant). The subjective disturbance level experienced by the researcher was assessed using a Likert scale from 1 to 7, with 1 being "not disturbing at all" and 7 being "very disturbing."

The materials used included writing tools and a timer. Electronic devices were avoided to prevent interference with the patient's rest. The data analysis involved manually transcribing the handwritten notes into a computer, and organizing, and classifying the information into tables and diagrams. The results were directly derived from this analysis.

The study was conducted using pen and paper because the technical resources to record sound and video in a non-intrusive manner were not available. It was the first approach focused on immersing in the context and was

considered a less intrusive option than a video camera recording the entire session.

2.2 Study 2 - Patients

The second phase aimed to explore hospitalized patients' sleep experiences in the neurology ward compared to their experiences at home, and to gauge their willingness to participate in the next phase of the Sleep Study replication.

A total of 7 patients participated, of whom 6 were men and 1 was a woman. Patients were recruited based on the ward supervisor's recommendation, selecting those physically and mentally capable of responding to the questions independently and rationally, and who had spent at least three nights hospitalized in the ward.

The experiment consisted of semi-structured, face-to-face interviews where patients answered open-ended questions or rated their responses on a Likert scale. These questions focused on comparing their sleep experiences in the hospital to those at home, identifying sound events, assessing their level of disturbance, and determining their willingness to participate in a second phase of the study involving sound recordings.

All interviews were recorded using a mobile phone and transcribed using the Transkriptor app, producing a PDF of the conversation. The transcripts were then manually cleaned and corrected to remove unnecessary data, off-topic comments, and transcription errors. No additional materials were required for this phase.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Study 1 - Environment

The aim of the study on the nocturnal sound environment at Miguel Servet Hospital in Zaragoza was to identify and analyze the sound sources present during the night and to document the physical layout of the rooms.

As previously mentioned, the study was conducted in a single-patient room occupied by the patient, a caregiver, and the researcher. The room was located midway down the corridor, between the central staff area (with the call button) and the end of the neurology ward. Adjacent rooms were also occupied by other patients. The layout and elements of the room are shown in the following diagram.

Figure 1. Diagram of a single-patient room

The patient's rest began at 9:00 PM when the lights were turned off, blinds lowered, and silence was maintained in the room. At this time, external noises were comparable to those during the daytime.

At 11:00 PM, the nurses conducted their first round of administering medication, followed shortly after by the nursing assistants, who checked on patients, changed diapers, and ensured everything was in order. From this point until 6:00 AM, when the first morning nursing round began, staff did not enter the rooms unless called.

The following tables summarize the sound events recorded during this period, as well as the previously mentioned interruptions, detailing their duration, frequency, and perceived disturbance level.

EVENTOS SONOROS	HORARIO	DURACIÓN	REPETICIÓN	NIVEL DE PERTURBACIÓN
Aire acondicionado	De 23:30 a 6:00	Constante	Constante	Bajo
Ruidos silla acompañantes	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneo	11	Bajo
Ruido movimiento paciente	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneo	6	Bajo
Timbre central	De 01:00 a 6:00	Segundos	2	Alto
Puertas	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneo	4	Alto
Golpes	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneos	3	Medio
Voces de externas a la habitación	De 23:30 a 6:00	Minutos	5	Alto
Pasos	De 23:30 a 6:00	Unos segundos	4	Bajo
Carrito de medicinas	23:00 y 6:00	Unos segundos	3	Alto
Voz paciente	De 23:30 a 6:00	Unos segundos	3	Alto
Ronquidos y suspiros	De 23:30 a 6:00	Constante	Constante	Medio
Tos	De 23:30 a 6:00	Momentáneo	5	Medio

Table 1. Sound events during a night shift

INTERRUPCIONES	HORARIO	DURACIÓN	REPETICIÓN	NIVEL DE PERTURBACIÓN
Enfermería medicamentos	23:06	45"	1	Muy alta
TCAE mirar pañal	23:21	1'30"	1	Muy alta
Vuelta para otros pacientes	00:06	10'	1	Muy alta
Ruido movimiento paciente	06:10	5'	1	Muy alta

Table 2. Interruptions during the patient's rest period

As observed, some events were more frequent throughout the night but were not necessarily the most disturbing or disruptive for the patient. Disturbance depended not only on the occurrence of these events but also on their intensity and duration.

3.2 Study 2 - Patients

The second study focused on assessing the sleep quality of patients and the sound events they perceived, as well as their willingness to participate in subsequent research phases.

Regarding sleep quality, most patients reported that their sleep in the hospital was inferior to their sleep at home. Key findings included:

- 6 out of 7 of patients reported more frequent sleep interruptions during their hospital stay.
- At home, patients averaged more hours of sleep, compared to the hours in the hospital.
- Only 2 out of 7 felt they achieved a quality of rest comparable to their home. One patient attributed this improvement to pain relief provided by medication.

The primary differences lay in involuntary interruptions, with patients describing greater difficulty maintaining continuous sleep in the hospital. Noise and medical interruptions were significant contributors to this discrepancy.

Patients identified several sources of noise or sleep disruptions during hospitalization. The most frequently mentioned were:

- Medical procedures: Activities by staff, such as entering rooms or handling devices, affected rest for 4 out of 7 of patients.
- Snoring: Mentioned as a nuisance by 2 out of 7 of patients in shared rooms.
- Caregivers or visitors: Reported as a moderate disturbance by 3 out of 7 of patients.
- Cart wheels: Noted as bothersome by 2 out of 7 of patients, though less frequently.

Specific noises, such as infusion pumps and air conditioning, were highlighted for their detectability even during quieter periods at night. However, 3 out of 7 stated that the general sound environment did not significantly disturb them, or they were able to adapt to it.

Regarding participation in studies related to hospital sound monitoring, responses varied:

- 4 out of 7 were willing to collaborate, provided the objectives were clear and recordings ensured confidentiality.
- 2 out of 7 expressed reluctance or refusal, citing privacy concerns or potential inconvenience.
- One patient was indifferent, remarking that "there's no need to record room sounds."

Patients who viewed such studies as beneficial emphasized the potential to improve the hospital environment and the rest experience for future patients. Clear and ongoing communication played a pivotal role

in achieving a "shared language" between researchers and participants. This was especially evident when addressing privacy concerns and explaining study objectives. For instance, one participant expressed initial hesitation about sound recordings but later agreed to participate after a detailed explanation of data confidentiality measures. Another patient emphasized the need for explicit communication about the purpose of the study, which researchers addressed by providing examples of how sound data could improve hospital practices. These efforts not only built trust but also helped align the understanding of both parties regarding the study's goals.

Challenges in communication arose primarily from the diversity of patients' backgrounds and health conditions, which required researchers to tailor their approach. For example, one participant, unfamiliar with digital recording methods, required additional clarification on how recordings would be managed and used. Similarly, patients in shared rooms sometimes had differing opinions on the intrusiveness of noise, requiring the team to mediate and establish a mutual understanding of acceptable study conditions. These examples demonstrate the iterative and collaborative process of creating a shared understanding, ultimately enabling meaningful engagement with the research.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight the profound impact of sound sources on the quality of sleep of hospitalized patients and reveal a multifaceted problem. Firstly, nocturnal sound events, such as medical alarms, healthcare staff activities, and environmental noises (carts, slamming doors, conversations), were identified as significant factors disrupting rest. The characterization of the hospital acoustic environment showed that not only sound intensity but also the regularity and psychoacoustic characteristics of the sounds affect subjective perception and patients' ability to rest. These results align with previous studies emphasizing the importance of designing acoustic environments to promote hospital well-being (NIH, 2021; Özcan et al., 2022).

As a contribution of this research, a series of actions are proposed to improve a sound ecosystem focused on the comprehensive well-being of patients and caregivers:

- Awareness and training. Develop educational programs not only for staff but also at the hospital level on the impact of noise and its management, integrating practical acoustic reduction guides. Awareness-raising sessions could be held on the individual and collective impact of each hospital agent's sound sources and noise and their effect on the patient's recovery and the optimal development of clinical activities.
- Technological interventions. One option could be to implement silent notification systems, such as visual alarms and alerts on mobile devices,

which do not necessarily need to be hospital equipment but could be an app installed on individual mobile devices. Additionally, tying in with the previous point on awareness, a visual sound meter could be implemented to indicate the state of the environment and encourage those present to be mindful of the noise they produce. An option might also be to integrate a device that could emit relaxing background sounds, such as white noise, adjustable to the patient's personal preferences.

- Redesign and maintenance of medical equipment. As much as possible, maintain equipment in good condition to avoid unnecessary noises such as squeaky cart wheels and low-noise operating medical equipment.
- Operational management focused on prioritizing patients' rest, coordinating medical rounds to minimize interruptions, and establish "quiet zones" during key rest hours.
- And having clear policies. Communicate to patients and staff the strategies and benefits of noise reduction measures to encourage their adoption.

Lastly, design specifications are written for the development of future quantitative research where sound events are recorded and correlated with patient sleep quality.

Patients' interests and needs lie in their own comfort. Evidently, they are the ones who are ill, and what they need is to achieve adequate rest to promote a quick recovery. As for the system for collecting and gathering sound information, accessible interfaces will be essential to allow customization of acceptable noise levels. An important aspect to consider is that the equipment should not interfere with the patient's activities, meaning it should neither obstruct nor inconvenience, trying to respect personal space. The device must be understandable to them or at least provide basic instructions or guidelines to allow them to stop recordings if they do not want the sound to be recorded at any time.

The findings of this study highlight the significant influence of sound events on the sleep quality of hospitalized patients. However, a noteworthy aspect is an observation that some participants do not perceive certain sounds as disruptive, raising questions about the inherent subjectivity of acoustic experiences and their impact on patients' well-being. This phenomenon underscores the importance of avoiding hasty generalizations unsupported by data, as noise perception varies significantly among individuals.

Personal context plays a key role in the interpretation of sound stimuli. Factors such as health status, prior experiences, expectations of the hospital environment,

and familiarity with ambient noise levels can modulate patients' responses to sound. For instance, a patient living in an urban environment may be more accustomed to high noise levels and therefore perceive hospital noise as less disruptive than someone from a quiet rural setting. Additionally, the emotional and physical state of patients, such as anxiety, pain, or the use of sedatives, can also influence their sensitivity to noise.

This finding has significant implications for designing interventions to improve the hospital's acoustic environment. Instead of adopting a uniform approach, it is necessary to consider the diversity of individual perceptions and adapt strategies to address the specific needs of different patient profiles. For example, providing customizable options, such as devices emitting white noise or relaxing sounds adjusted to the patient's preferences, could be a more effective and respectful measure of individual variations.

On the other hand, the variability in noise perception also presents methodological challenges for research. Future studies should be designed to capture this subjectivity, possibly using qualitative tools such as in-depth interviews or self-report scales that explore how personal context and patient experiences influence their perceptions. Additionally, it is suggested to complement these data with objective measurements, such as electronically recorded noise levels, to contrast and enrich the understanding of the acoustic environment's impact.

Regarding the study's limitations, we highlight a limited sample size; the small sample restricts the generalization of the findings. We must also address data collection bias; the absence of electronic devices in the first study may have influenced the accuracy of sound event recording. Additionally, the complexity of the acoustic environment presents challenges, as the multiple sources and characteristics of hospital sounds make isolating key variables difficult. Another critical limitation is the study's focus on individual patient rooms. Conducting the research in shared rooms would likely introduce additional noise sources, such as interactions between roommates, visitors, and overlapping medical procedures, which were not considered in this study. Lastly, the subjectivity and perspective of the patient must be noted, as some results reflect individual adaptations to noise, potentially underestimating the broader impact of certain sound sources. These factors underscore the need for further research with larger, more diverse samples and methodological approaches that address the complexities of shared hospital environments.

In conclusion, we can affirm that this study provides a valuable initial framework for addressing the impact of the sound environment in hospitals, although future quantitative research will be essential to validate the proposed interventions and extend their applicability. It also emphasizes the need to critically address individual

perceptions. Recognizing and respecting differences in how patients experience sound will not only strengthen the validity of future research but also enable the design of more inclusive and effective interventions that promote the overall well-being of patients in hospital settings.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study provides significant insights into the relationship between the hospital soundscape and the sleep quality of hospitalized patients, contributing to a growing body of research on optimizing rest in medical settings. The findings confirm that nocturnal sound events adversely affect sleep quality, with implications for both physical and mental recovery. The study emphasizes that sound intensity, frequency, and psychoacoustic characteristics are key determinants of patients' subjective perception and their ability to rest.

The research also highlights the multifaceted nature of the problem, requiring a holistic approach to address the needs of diverse stakeholders, including patients, healthcare professionals, and design teams. Proposed solutions include fostering awareness and training programs for hospital staff, implementing adaptive technologies such as silent alarms and personalized soundscapes, and redesigning medical equipment and hospital environments to minimize noise disruptions. Furthermore, operational strategies, such as optimizing medical rounds and creating "quiet zones," are essential for supporting uninterrupted rest.

Importantly, this research underscores the value of user-centered methodologies and interdisciplinary collaboration in developing effective and practical interventions. While the study was limited by its small sample size and the subjective nature of certain findings, it establishes a robust framework for future quantitative investigations, particularly in correlating sound events with objective measures of sleep quality.

By prioritizing a shared language among stakeholders and fostering the co-creation of innovative solutions, this research paves the way for redefining hospital acoustic environments. Ultimately, these efforts aim to enhance patient well-being, optimize recovery outcomes, and establish new standards for patient-centered care in healthcare facilities.

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